

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN SOCIOCULTURAL SPHERE

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Annotation: This article discusses the specific of introducing a sociocultural approach into teaching a foreign language. Using the sociocultural approach in language education allows us to discover in a new, deeper and more meaningful way all the components of the concept of the level of functional sociocultural literacy.

Key: culture; sociocultural approach; teaching a foreign language; education; foreign language component; process

Teaching a foreign language in the context of culture is a problem of our time. In recent decades, changes have taken place in the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages, associated with the intensification of the search for new approaches to teaching and learning a language. One of the most important areas is an intercultural approach to teaching foreign languages.

In particular, more and more attention has recently been paid to the sociocultural component of the content of teaching a foreign language. Appeal to the problem of the socio-cultural content of education is due to the new goal of teaching a foreign language - the formation of a linguistic personality capable of carrying out foreign language activities in an intercultural context. Since the main object is not the structure of the language, but the ability to produce intercultural understanding, the sociocultural component of the content of teaching a foreign language is an integral part of the content of foreign language education.

The sociocultural approach most clearly demonstrates the process of intercultural interaction, since it is associated not only with the concepts of a common or national culture, but also with the customs of the social sphere, stereotypes of everyday life. Ignoring the sociocultural aspect of communication in the learning process leads to errors, the main categories of which are distinguished at the level of sociocultural background knowledge of speech behavior of speech culture. The use of a sociocultural approach in language education allows us to reveal in a new way, more deeply and meaningfully all the components of the concept of the level of functional sociocultural literacy.

The sociocultural approach is a concept that captures the understanding of culture as a wide range of social phenomena that are the results and means of social functioning and development.

It is necessary to develop the student's self-knowledge as a cultural and historical subject. "globalization", humanization, ecologization and cultural sociologization of the content of language education.

Thus, the result of sociocultural education is sociocultural competence, the successful formation of which is possible with the use of sociocultural competence.

Sociocultural competence is a part of foreign language communicative competence, which is understood as a certain level of mastery of the "technique" of communication, the assimilation of certain norms, stereotypes of behavior. Foreign language communicative competence is inextricably linked with the cognitive and emotional development of the student and includes, in turn, several of its components: speech, language, sociocultural, compensatory, educational and cognitive competencies, which are based on knowledge, skills, abilities and relationships

It is hardly possible to overestimate the role of sociocultural competence in foreign language education. Sociocultural competence - the student's willingness and ability to build his intercultural communication based on the knowledge of the culture of the people of the country of the language being studied, its traditions, mentality, customs within the framework of topics, areas, situations of communication that meet the interests of students at different stages of education; willingness to compare native culture and the culture of the countries of the language being studied, to highlight the common and different in cultures, to explain these differences to representatives of another culture. In other words, socio-cultural competence is the totality of knowledge about the country of the language being studied, the national and cultural characteristics of the social and speech behavior of native speakers and the ability to use such knowledge in the process of communication, following the customs, rules of conduct, norms of etiquette, social conditions and behavior stereotypes of native speakers.

At present, in accordance with the needs of society, the sociocultural aspect, as an integral component of teaching a foreign language, is becoming increasingly relevant in the light of the intensification of intercultural communications, it is about cultural literacy, which includes not only knowledge of the culture of one's country, but also cultural literacy within the world At present, in accordance with the needs of society, the sociocultural aspect, as an integral component of teaching a foreign language, is becoming increasingly relevant in the light of the intensification of intercultural communications, it is

about cultural literacy, which includes not only knowledge of the culture of one's country, but also cultural literacy within the world. In the modern world, the problem of mutual understanding between peoples is becoming more and more acute, so it is very important that there are no difficulties due to the clash of different cultures due to different historical, political and socio-cultural development. At present, the establishment and development of international and intercultural contacts and ties is one of the most acute social problems in all spheres of public life of the world community. The study of foreign languages and their use as a means of international communication is impossible without a deep and versatile knowledge of the culture of the speakers of these languages, their mentality, national character, lifestyle, vision of the world, customs, traditions, social behavior. Only the combination of these two knowledge - the language and culture of our partners in the world community can provide an effective and fruitful process of educational adaptation should take place without prejudice to the national identity and personal dignity of students. In the pedagogical literature, this educational problem appears as learning in the form of a dialogue of cultures. The nature of the interrelationships of the universal, international and national is reflected in the concept of "multicultural education", which meets the needs of the development and self-realization of a person in a new socio-cultural situation. In order to teach students not only to express their thoughts grammatically correctly, but also to lay the foundations for culturally competent speech behavior for them, it is necessary to deepen the knowledge of culture itself. And this is not about a simple shift of emphasis from the universal elements of the language to the cultural and historical specifics of the community that communicates in the language being studied, but about the need for both parallel teaching according to the "language-culture" model and the organic inclusion of a block of socio-cultural knowledge in the educational process. Taking into account that the main goal of teaching foreign languages is foreign language communication and access to communication with representatives of other cultures in the most diversified state prepared for this, the problem of including a sociocultural component in the process of teaching a foreign language becomes especially relevant. The similarity or difference of cultures affects the mutual understanding of communicants who compare themselves and "ours", which leads to the well-known formula "us and them". Meanwhile, the intensive development of intercultural communication at different levels, the awareness of belonging to a single European space requires the achievement of understanding between speakers of different languages and

cultures. The practical needs of intercultural communication set the direction of new theoretical searches and lead to a rethinking of established and traditional approaches to teaching foreign languages. The object of this study is the socio-cultural component of the content of education and the teaching activity of the teacher in the formation of the communicative competence of students.

The purpose of the study: to reveal the content and specifics of the socio-cultural component in teaching a foreign language, as well as its role in increasing the motivation for learning a foreign language in the context of the planned modernization of education that meets the needs of modern life and the needs of the development of the individual and society.

To achieve this goal, it was supposed to solve the following tasks:

1. To study and summarize the research available in the methodology of teaching a foreign language on this issue and find possible reserves for their accumulation, in this case through the disclosure of the concept of "sociocultural component";
2. Show the specifics and significance of this component to increase the motivation for learning a foreign language as the basis of multicultural education;
3. To check, on the basis of an experimental study of the learning process, the legitimacy of this approach to the renewing content of education on a multicultural basis.

As a hypothesis, the statement is put forward that the sociocultural component really serves as an incentive to increase the motivation for learning a foreign language and a means of teaching a foreign culture. In this case, the construction of a training course is possible under the following conditions:

taking into account the basic requirements and principles of multicultural education;

relying on the world experience of pedagogical linguistic and regional studies;

studies of the course of pedagogical linguistic and regional studies not only for learning the language, but also for the holistic adaptation of the individual to the country of the language being studied;

- application of student-centered education technologies when implementing the course.

To solve the above problems, the following research methods were used: theoretical analysis of the literature on the problem under consideration, questioning, interviewing, observation (direct and indirect, self-observation) of the pedagogical process, conversation, and experiential learning.

Any communication is accompanied by various paralinguistic elements, that is, facial expressions, postures, gestures. Then hands (gestures), face (facial expressions), symbols (wedding ring), signals (clothing and e) and body movement speak.

The set of norms and traditions of friendliness, reflecting the recommended rules of communication that have developed in society due to historical traditions, rituals, social situations, including facial expressions, gestures, postures of those who communicate, is called non-verbal communicative behavior or non-verbal language (silent language of communication).

Non-verbal languages are important not only for communication, but above all for the formation of the student's inner world and his attitude to the native speakers of the studied verbal language, to their culture, to their way of life. In this regard, the language of everyday behavior is especially important.

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